

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DETERMINATION OF BIO PHARMACEUTICAL COMPONENTS OF A NOVEL POLY HERBAL FORMULATION BY GC – MS ANALYSIS.

S. Selvakumar^{*}, J. Sindhuja

Department of Industrial BioTechnology, Bharath University, Chennai-600073, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 10/10/2017

Available online

06/12/2017

Keywords

Novel Hebal Formulation,
Bio Pharmaceutical,
Gas Chromatography,
Drug Discovery,
Active Principles.

ABSTRACT

The present study aims to investigate and characterize the chemical composition of the chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation was studied. The air dried plant materials were powdered and further subjected to gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. Qualitative determination of the different Pharmacologically and biologically active compounds from chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry revealed different types of high and low molecular weight chemical entities with varying quantities present in the extract. These chemical compounds are considered biologically and pharmacologically important. Furthermore, the chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation possess unique physicochemical characteristics which may be attributed to the compounds naturally present in significant quantities in the herbal formulation. The chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation possess 13 major bioactive compounds that were identified and characterized spectroscopically. Hence, identification of different bio pharmacologically active compounds may warrants further biological and pharmacological studies.

Corresponding author

Dr. S.Selvakumar

Ph.D.,

Associate Professor,

Department of Industrial BioTechnology,

Bharath University,

Chennai-600073, India.

+91-9840917984.

selvakumarmss@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Dr. S.Selvakumar** et al. Determination of Bio Pharmaceutical Components of A Novel Poly Herbal Formulation by Gc – Ms Analysis. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(11).

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION

The recent research in new drug discovery from medicinal plants involves a multifaceted approach combining botanical, phytochemical, biological, and molecular techniques. Medicinal plant drug discovery continues to provide new and important leads against various pharmacological targets including cancer. The most important aim of medical science in this century is the prevention, cure and mitigation of cancer. For the past many decades, there have been extensive efforts to evaluate the chemotherapeutic role of substances present in natural products [1]. Traditional medicinal plants are routinely used by traditional healers to treat a variety of diseases including diabetes melitus and cancer. According to the World Health Organization, over 80% of the world's populations rely upon such traditional plant-based systems of medicine to provide them primary healthcare [2]. Dietary intake of phytochemical has been associated with decreased risk of cancer and significant survivability of cancer patients. Over 60% of anticancer drugs available in the market are of natural origin. Natural chemical moieties are lead molecules for many of the drugs that are currently in use [3].

The genus *Hugonia L.* of family Linaceae comprise about 40 species in the world; of which *Hugonia mystax L.* was reported from India. This plant *Hugonia mystax* is locally known as Modirakanni. Ethnobotanically, the fruits are used by the tribals of Kalakad Mundanthurai for the treatment of Rheumatism[4]. This medicinal plant roots were used as anthelmintic, astringent and also used for dysentery, snake bite, fever, rheumatism and inflammations. Biological activities such as analgesic, anti-inflammatory and ulcerogenic were reported [5]. *Wedelia* is an extensive genus of the family Asteraceae, comprising about 60 different species. *Wedelia trilobata* Linn. has long been used as traditional herbal medicine in South America, China, Japan, India and for the treatment of a variety of ailments. The aerial parts of this plant are used in traditional medicine in the Caribbean and Central America against bronchitis, colds, abdominal pains, dysmenorrheal and even as a fertility enhancer [6]. In folk medicine, it is employed to treat backache, muscle cramps, rheumatism, stubborn wounds, sores and swellings, and arthritic painful joints [7]. The Miskito Indians of eastern Nicaragua use leaves for treatment of kidney dysfunctioning, cold, stingray wounds, snakebite, purge and amenorrhea [8]. The fruits, leaves and stem are used in childbirth and in the treatment of bites and stings, fever and infection [9]. In Trinidad and Tobago, used for reproductive problems, amenorrhea, dysmenorrheal and it is used for the treatment of fever and malaria in Vietnam [10]. *Cassia alata* Linn. belongs to the family of Caesalpiniaceae and is a large shrub with thick downy branches, found wild almost throughout India. Leaflets are 8-12 pairs, lower leaflet oblong-elliptic; upper ones broadly obovate. It is known as Ringworm shrub and winged senna in English; Dadruhna and Dvipagsti in Sanskrit; semaiagathi and Vandugolli in Tamil [11]. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the pharmaceutically important bio active principles from chloroformic extract of a novel poly herbal formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of medicinal plants

The powder form of poly herbal formulation were used for this study contains the equal volume of shade dried leaves of *Hugonia syntax*, *Wedelia trilobata* and *Cassia alata* were collected from the near by medicinal gardens, Chennai, India. The parts of the plants was authenticated by botanist and herbal formulation were prepared by as the available literature.

Plant Materials

The Chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation (Powder form) were used for this study.

Preparation of Plant extracts

The extraction of the poly herbal powder was carried out using known standard procedures. The plant materials were dried in shade and powdered in a mechanical grinder. The powder (25.0 g) of the plant materials were initially defatted with petroleum ether (60-80°C), followed by 900 ml of hydroalcohol by using a Soxhlet extractor for 72 hours at a temperature not exceeding the boiling point of the solvent. The extracts were filtered using Whatman filter paper (No.1) while hot, concentrated in vacuum under reduced pressure using rotary flask evaporator, and dried in a desiccator. The hydroalcoholic extract yields a dark greenish solid residue weighing 5.750 g (23.0% w/w). More yields of extracts were collected by this method of extractions. The extracts were then kept in sterile bottles, under refrigerated conditions, until further use. The dry weight of the plant extracts was obtained by the solvent evaporation and used to determine concentration in mg/ml. The extract was preserved at 2- to 4°C. This crude extracts of hydroalcohol was used for further investigations

Chemicals and Reagents

All chemicals were used for this project were purchased from M/s. Sigma Chemicals, USA.

GC-MS analysis of Chloroform extract of *Nalla Marunthu*.

Preparation of plant extract

25 grams of the poly herbal powder were soaked in 95% chloroform for 12 hrs. The extract was then filtered through Whatman filter paper along with 2gm sodium sulfate to remove the sediments and traces of water in the filtrate. Before filtering, the filter paper was made wet with 95% ethanol along with sodium sulphate. The filtrate was then concentrated by bubbling nitrogen gas into the solution. The extract contained both polar and non-polar phyto-components in the plant material. 2µl of this solution was employed for GC-MS analysis. The herbal powder was extracted with chloroform and analyzed using GC-MS (GC Clarius 500 Perkin Elmer) analyzer. The data were obtained on an Elite-1(100% Dimethyl poly siloxane) column (30 0.25mm 1µm df). Helium (99.999%) was used as the carrier gas with a flow rate of 1ml/min in the split mode (10:1). An aliquot of 2µl of ethanol solution of the sample was injected into the column with the injector temperature at 250°C. GC oven temperature started at 110°C and holding for 2min and it

was raised to 200°C at the rate of 10°C/min, without holding. Holding was allowed at 280°C for 9 min with program rate of 5°C/min. The injector and detector temperatures were set at 250°C and 280°C respectively. Ion source temperature was maintained at 200°C. The mass spectrum of compounds in samples was obtained by electron ionization at 70 eV and the detector was operated in scan mode from 45-450amu (atomic mass units). A scan interval of 0.5seconds and fragments from 45 to 450 Da was maintained. The total running time was 36minutes [12].

Identification of components

Identification was based on the molecular structure, molecular mass and calculated fragments. Interpretation on mass spectrum GC-MS was conducted using the database of National Institute Standard and Technology (NIST) having more than 62,000 patterns. The name, molecular weight and structure of the components of the test materials were ascertained. The relative percentage amount of each component was calculated by comparing its average peak area to the total areas. The spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the component stored in the NIST library version (2005), software, Turbomas 5.2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Indian system of medicines systems the leaves of *C.alata* plant are used as purgative, expectorant astringent, vermicide and to treat all skin diseases. Extracts of *Cassia alata* leaves have been reported to possess analgesics anti-bacterial [13]. antiinflammatory [14]. Anti fungal activities [15]. Anti diabetic [16]. Ayurveda is one of the traditional system of Indian medicine. The philosophy behind ayurveda is preventing unnecessary suffering and living a long healthy life. Ayurveda involves the use of natural elements to eliminate the root cause of the disease

Figure 1 shows that the chromatogram of chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation.

Qualitative Analysis Report

Data Filename	T1703008-02.D	Sample Name	N200317017
Sample Type		Position	10
Instrument Name		User Name	
Acq Method	All compounds Screening Methods.M	Acquired Time	21-Mar-17 7:14:05 PM
IRM Calibration Status	Not Applicable	DA Method	l.m

Comment

Expected Barcode		Sample Amount	
Dual Inj Vol	2	TuneName	atunes.eiex.tune.xml
TunePath	D:\MassHunter\GCMS\1\7000	TuneDateStamp	13-Feb-17 9:12:24 AM
	\Tune		
	Reports\AutoTune_20170213		
	_090406		
MSFirmwareVersion	DSP: 7000.3000, qqServer: Acquisition Time #2 2017-03-21 13:44:05Z		
	G.7000.046-RUN		
OperatorName		RunCompletedFlag	True
Acquisition SW	MassHunter GC/MS		
Version	Acquisition B.07.01.1805 12-		
	Mar-2014 Copyright © 1989-		
	2014 Agilent Technologies,		
	Inc.		

Table:1 shows that the Retention Time, Height and Area percentage of chemical components in the chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation.

Integration Peak List

Peak	Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	Area Sum Percet
1	5.127	5.154	5.177	6066685	7091770	2.29	0.57
2	5.261	5.279	5.294	3366499	3357615	1.08	0.27
3	5.302	5.318	5.332	2627834	2352728	0.76	0.19
4	5.363	5.383	5.407	2911738	3365724	1.09	0.27
5	5.537	5.59	5.629	30926876	35579813	11.5	2.86
6	5.749	5.792	5.807	19102711	22269441	7.2	1.79
7	5.848	5.892	5.912	3846494	3669323	1.19	0.29
8	5.935	5.955	5.978	48064664	56259331	18.18	4.52
9	5.985	6.003	6.018	9961346	9840330	3.18	0.79
10	6.042	6.055	6.083	17629172	20073247	6.49	1.61
11	6.122	6.18	6.211	5827301	11507287	3.72	0.92
12	6.531	6.554	6.612	3597208	5855358	1.89	0.47
13	6.624	6.652	6.673	4600632	6080874	1.96	0.49
14	6.98	7.027	7.042	7141239	11149591	3.6	0.9
15	7.601	7.658	7.708	8251655	14841638	4.8	1.19
16	8.432	8.466	8.507	3153278	5476721	1.77	0.44
17	10.958	11.031	11.087	4222517	9258949	2.99	0.74
18	12.681	12.774	12.84	21815558	55889293	18.06	4.49
19	13.74	13.858	13.95	14638577	30542860	9.87	2.45
20	16.289	16.413	16.453	11892225	35158865	11.36	2.82
21	16.479	16.519	16.611	17758081	55627671	17.97	4.47
22	17.617	17.682	17.731	8867640	31387897	10.14	2.52
23	18.609	18.661	18.697	5596091	14867294	4.8	1.19
24	23.165	23.237	23.279	12057283	31531314	10.19	2.53
25	23.643	23.715	23.788	13719891	37418823	12.09	3
26	27.086	27.152	27.212	8988407	27031081	8.73	2.17
27	28.508	28.619	28.685	22342342	60569092	19.57	4.86
28	29.252	29.316	29.351	18873973	51446530	16.62	4.13
29	29.62	29.675	29.73	11242165	28772209	9.3	2.31
30	30.119	30.195	30.271	81257335	309494010	100	24.85
31	30.685	30.77	30.876	9785787	42253337	13.65	3.39
32	31.317	31.434	31.5	50562576	205454910	66.38	16.5

Table:2 shows that the presence of chemical components in the chloroform extract of a novel poly herbal formulation.

S.no	Retention Time	Name of the chemical components	Molecular structure	Molecular Weight
1	5.154	Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)-	$C_{20}H_{38}O_2$	310.52
2	5.279	Ethyl iso allochololate	$C_{26}H_{44}O_5$	436.62
3	5.318	Ethyl iso allochololate	$C_{26}H_{44}O_5$	436.62
4	5.383	Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)-	$C_{20}H_{38}O_2$	310.52
5	5.59	Caryophyllene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.35

6	5.792	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid,(z-z)-	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	278.43
7	5.892	Butyl 6,9,12-hexadecatrienoate	C ₂₀ H ₃₄	306.48
8	5.955	Copaene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.35
9	6.003	Phenol,3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	206.32
10	6.055	Cyclohexane,1-ethenyl-1-methyl-2-(1-methyl lethyl)-4-(1-methylethyl-idene)-	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.35
11	6.18	Alpha-acorenal	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O	222.37
12	6.554	Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)-	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₂	310.52
13	6.652	Cis 5,8,11,14,17-Ecosapentaenoic acid	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ O ₂	302.45
14	7.027	6-epi-shyobunol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	222.37
15	7.658	Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)-	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₂	310.52
16	8.466	Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)-	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₂	310.52
17	11.031	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
18	12.774	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
19	13.858	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
20	16.413	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
21	16.519	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
22	17.682	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
23	18.661	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
24	23.237	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
25	23.715	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45
26	27.152	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
27	28.619	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
28	29.316	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
29	29.675	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
30	30.195	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
31	30.77	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89
32	31.434	1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ O ₄ Si ₂	498.89

By restoring balance, at the same time create a healthy life-style to prevent the recurrence of imbalance [17]. The Chloroform extract of a novel polyherbal formulation *Nalla marunthu* contains 13 various phytoconstituents [18]. such as Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)- (Area %2.29), Ethyl iso allocholate (1.08%), Caryophyllene (11.5%), 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid,(z-z)- (7.2%), Butyl 6,9,12-hexadecatrienoate (Area 1.19%), Copaene (18.18), Phenol,3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-(3.18 %). Cyclohexane,1-ethenyl-1-methyl-2-(1-methyl lethyl)-4-(1-methylethyl-idene)-(6.49), Alpha-acorenal (3.72%), Cis 5,8,11,14,17-Ecosapentaenoic acid (1.96), 6-epi-shyobunol, Ethanol,2-(9,12-octadecadienyloxy)-(z-z)- (3.36), The peak number 17-25 represents the component 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (z-z) (The area % were 2.99-12.09). The peak number 26-32 represents the phyto component 1-Monolinoleoylglyceroltrimethylsilyl the minimum area percentage are 8.73 to 66.38. Herbal medicines have existed globally with long recorded history and they were used in ancient Indian, Chinese and Arabian system medicines for various therapeutic purposes. In ayurveda system of medicine single or multiple herbal plants such as polyherbal formulations were used for the treatment and highlighted the concept of polyherbalism to achieve greater therapeutic efficacy. The active phytochemical constituents of individual plants are insufficient to achieve the desirable therapeutic effects. When combining the multiple herbs in a particular ratio, it will give a better therapeutic effect and reduce the toxicity [19]. Drug formulation in ayurveda is based on two principles: Use as a single drug and use of more than one drugs, in which the latter is known as polyherbal formulation [20]. This vital traditional therapeutic herbal medicinal strategy exploits the combining of several medicinal herbs or parts of herbal plants to achieve extra therapeutic effectiveness, usually known as polypharmacy or polyherbalism.

CONCLUSION

The chloroform extract of a novel polyherbal formulation possess major bioactive compounds that were identified and characterized spectroscopically. Hence, identification of different bio pharmacologically active compounds may warrants further biological and pharmacological studies.

REFERENCES

1. Calixto J B, Twenty five years of research on medicinal plants in Latin America: a personal review, J Ethnopharmacol 2005; 100: 131-34.
2. Ho J W, Leung Y K, Chan C P. Herbal medicine in the treatment of cancer, Curr. Med Chem. Anti Cancer Agents 2002; 2:209-14.
3. Cragg G M, Newman D J, Snader K M. Natural products in drug discovery and development. J Nat Prod 1997; 60 (1): 52- 60.
4. Sutha S, Mohan V R., Kumaresan S , Murugan C and Athiperumalsami T . Ethnomedicinal plants used by the tribals of Kalakad Mundanthurai Tiger Reserve (KMTR), Western Ghats, Tamil Nadu for the treatment of rheumatism. Ind J Traditional Knowl 2009; 9 :502-09.

5. Dhivaharan V , Madhavan S , Balu S . Ethnobotany of Point Calimere Wildlife Sanctuary, Tamil Nadu: A preliminary survey. *Adv Plant Sci* 2008; 21 : 343-45.
6. Coe F G. and Anderson G J . Screening of medicinal plants used by the Garifuna of eastern Nicaragua for bioactive compounds. *J Ethnopharmacol* 1996; 53 : 29-50.
7. Arvigo R and Balik M . *Rainforest Remedies, One Hundred Healing Herbs of Belize, USA: Lotus Press, Twin Lakes, WI, 1993.*
8. Duke J. *American agricultural research service-phytochemical and ethnobotanical Database, 2002.*
9. Lans C . Ethnomedicines used in Trinidad and Tobago for reproductive problems. *J Ethnobiol Ethnomed* 2007; 3: 13-25.
10. That Q T, Jossang J, Jossang A , Kim P P and Jaureguiberry G, Wedelolides A . A and B: Novel sesquiterpene -lactones, (9R)-eudesman-9, 12-olides, from *Wedelia trilobata* *J Org Chem* 2007; 72: 7102–7105.
11. Chopra R N, Nayar SL , and Chopra IC. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal plant: Publication and information Directorate, CSIR, New Delhi, 1986, p.54.*
12. Merlin N J, Parthasarathy V , Manavala R and Kumaravel S . Chemical investigation of aerial parts of *Gmelina asiatica* Linn by GC-MS, *Pharmacog Res* 2009 ; 1(3) :152-156
13. Ibrahim D, Osman H. Antimicrobial activity of *Cassia alata* from Malaysia, *J Ethnopharmacol* 1995; 45(3): 151-6.
14. Abatan M O. A note on the anti-inflammatory action of plants of some *Cassia* species, *Fitoterapia* 1990; 61 (4) :336-38.
15. Iyengar M A, Rama Rao MP , Gurumadhava Rao S, and . Kamath M S. Antiinflammatory activity of volatile oil of *Curcuma longa* L. leaves. *Indian drugs* 1994; 31 (1) 528- 31.
16. Palanichamy S, Nagarajan S , Devasagayam M. Effect of *Cassia alata* leaf extract on hyperglycemic rats. *J Ethnopharmacol* 1988; 22(1) : 81-90.
17. Khalsa K P , Tierra M. *The Way of Ayurvedic Herbs: The Complete Guide to Natural Healing and Health with Traditional Ayurvedic Herbalism. Lotus Press; 2008. USA.*
18. Ronald Hites A. *Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy: Handbook of Instrumental Techniques for Analytical Chemistry. 1997; 1: 609-11.*
19. Pal S K , Shukla Y . Herbal medicine: Current status and the future. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 2003; 4: 281–8.
20. Meena A K, Bansal P , . Kumar S . Plants herbal wealth as a potential source of ayurvedic drugs. *Asian J Tradit Med* 2009; 4 :152–70.

54878478451171008

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

